

Neuropil – a distributed, privacy-preserving, search index structure

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Abstract

Neuropil is an open-source de-centralized messaging layer that focuses on security and privacy by design. Persons, machines, and applications first have to identify their respective partners and/or content before real information can be sent. The discovery is handled internally and is based on so called "intent messages" that are secured by cryptographic primitives. Our project aims to create distributed search engine capabilities based on neuropil, that enable the discovery and sharing of information with significantly higher levels of trust and privacy and with more control over the search content for data owners than today's standard.

Setting The Scene

As of now large search engines have implemented "crawlers", that constantly visit webpages and categorize their content. The only way to somehow influence the information that is used by search engines is by using a file called „robots.txt“. Details about algorithms and especially their parameters are only known to the search engine provider. Furthermore there are a couple of misalignments in this model: Content hosted at a central search engine provider is probably outdated. Any search engine provider has to grow with the size of the connected information sources, which triples energy costs: not only the data owner holds information on his servers or electronic devices, the search engine provider needs to crawl the information and needs to store a copy of the material obtained. And although all this happens, nobody can be sure whether his information will appear as a search result: any search engine provider can (and for some parts must) withhold certain information, e.g. due to legal constraints.

A Different Approach

The neuropil messaging layer already uses a highly standardized "intent" format that protects the real content of users, i.e. the public keys contained in the intent messages are used to encrypt before any content is sent. These digitally secured "intent" (loosely modelled after JWT) are the public parts of the messaging layer, and therefore can be shared without any impact on copyrights. Using these "intent" token the above mentioned model is reversed: data owners define the searchable public content, and data users can discover available data sources. Because data owners would like to be found, we ask them to host a proportion of our new, distributed data structure: Based on the available "intent" token we derive cryptographic long term key (based on CLKHash* / PPRL**) and a new index hash (based on mmhash / LSH / LPH), which allows to distribute data in a privacy

* see also <https://clckhash.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>

** [Efficient private record linkage of very large datasets](#)

preserving, secure manner and thus enable each user / data owner to participate and maintain a search index and contents. We believe that it is thus possible to build a distributed search engine database that is able to contain and reveal any kind of information in a distributed, concise and privacy preserving manner, without the need for any central search engine provider.

Status Quo

In 2019 our project has received funding from the NGI ZeroDiscovery project. As part of this project we have not only improved the way how discovery for specific data models work, we also have implemented the required search capabilities in terms of algorithms and data structures into the Neuropil messaging layer. Our current experiments simulate a distributed setup ranging from 256 to 4096 nodes, and works well on smaller datasets. On a standard PC we are able to distribute one million of data records, and achieve a query time of ten milliseconds, but our code is running without any optimizations which leaves room for improvement.

The Road Ahead

In the upcoming months we would like to utilize larger datasets, in terms of "number of records", "number of index entries" and "data size" to validate our distributed structure. We are also looking out to distribute the created index structure throughout our Neuropil network. Even if our index structures is keeping its promises, we already see a couple of open questions that we have not been evaluated yet: Will energy consumption in our fully distributed setup be really less than crawling sites? Managing trust in such a setting will require new paradigms beyond PKI / Web Of Trust, but as of now we think that TSA (Time Stamping Authority) could be a way to move forward. How can a synchronized understanding of time between all nodes be established. And how can illegal content be banned from the search index? How will it be possible to establish such a distributed structure, when different organizations and data-owners are co-creating and participating a fully distributed setup? As of now we could just end up with a few more technical capabilities.

Our Presentation

In our OSF presentation we will show our work in terms of algorithms, data structures and communication topologies so far. We hope that we are able to conclude our NGI Zero Discovery project until October, so that participants can experiment and add content with our implementation themselves. We also would like to give an outlook how our approach could work in alignment with other technical initiatives (crawling / pipelining / preprocessing) in the OSF-Technology working group.